

Communication and Dissemination Plan

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Executive Summary

D7.1 presents the Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Plan for **ARXIVE (Advanced Research and eXploration for Interoperable Value in European Heritage)** (2026-2028).

The C&D Plan is structured around the 5W framework (Why, Who, What, Where/How, When) and covers four interconnected areas. The **Communication and Dissemination Framework** (Section 1) defines six strategic C&D objectives: maximising visibility, ensuring high-quality Open Call participation, disseminating scientific excellence, supporting policy uptake, building ecosystem synergies, and ensuring long-term sustainability. It maps target audience groups across primary, secondary, and tertiary tiers, specifies tailored key messages and engagement goals, and details the full range of communication channels, including the project website, LinkedIn, YouTube, Instagram, press releases, scientific publications, webinars. Activities are phased across four stages spanning the full 36-month project duration.

The **Open Call Promotion Strategy** (Section 2) outlines the multi-channel approach for promoting the two FSTP Open Calls: “Bibliography Beyond Boundaries” and “Building Digital Narratives”, each offering up to 10 lump-sum grants of €20,000. **Governance and Partner Responsibilities** (Section 3) establishes clear roles for all consortium members, with INOVA+ as WP7 leader coordinating all C&D activities in close alignment with LUH and the wider consortium.

The **Monitoring, KPIs and Evaluation** framework (Section 4) sets measurable targets across all channels, including website traffic, social media reach, scientific publications, policy briefs, training outreach, and ECCCH ecosystem engagement, with quarterly monitoring and adaptive evaluation mechanisms.

Introduction

ARXIVE (Advanced Research and eXploration for Interoperable Value in European Heritage) is a 36-month project (2026-2028) coordinated by Leibniz Universität Hannover (LUH), made up of a consortium of 9 partners (LUH, FORTH, Fraunhofer FIT, Open Knowledge Foundation Greece, INOVA+, EURECAT, National Library of Greece, Museums e Monumentos de Portugal, and ViLabs) dedicated to advancing the documentation, analysis, and dissemination of cultural heritage objects by developing cutting-edge tools and methodologies integrated into the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH).

ARXIVE's mission is to support cultural heritage professionals in capturing richer, more context-aware data about heritage objects, and to ensure that this information is interoperable, sustainable, and widely accessible, enhancing research, preservation practice, and public engagement.

Project Objectives

- **Develop Advanced Digital Tools:** Create innovative tools and methodologies integrated within the ECCCH for better documentation and semantic annotation of both tangible and intangible cultural heritage.
- **Improve Documentation and Interoperability:** Provide cultural heritage professionals with capabilities for semantically rich, context-aware documentation, integrating 3D reconstructions, annotation systems, AI-based bibliography tools, and narrative construction applications.
- **Support Collaboration and Standards Adoption:** Ensure solutions are interoperable with existing standards and principles, facilitating collaboration across institutions and long-term data sustainability.
- **Validate Solutions in Real-World Pilots:** Test and validate tools through two use-case pilots in Greece and Portugal, demonstrating effectiveness in actual heritage environments.
- **Build a Strategic Heritage Ecosystem:** Engage a multidisciplinary consortium and align with related ECCCH initiatives to amplify impact and position European cultural heritage at the forefront of digital innovation.

Key Actions

- Development of a meta ontology for aligning existing CHO vocabularies, enhancing annotation and archival processes.
- Creation of tools for automating the retrieval and annotation of bibliographies, improving efficiency for cultural heritage professionals.
- Scalable systems for storing, retrieving, and visualising large datasets related to 3D reconstructions, bibliographies, and excavation metadata.
- Sustainable data pipelines for continuous integration with versioning and provenance, ensuring long-term data integrity and traceability.

- Modern interfaces for annotating, narrating, and visualising digital cultural heritage assets, improving usability for professionals.
- Dynamic linking of bibliographic references with excavation contexts, enhancing granularity and contextualisation of annotations.
- Cross-domain and cross-application interoperability to ensure seamless integration with the ECCCH ecosystem and external repositories.
- Smooth onboarding and upskilling of cultural heritage professionals through co-creation of learning materials and training modules.

Document Scope and Structure

This document presents the Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Plan for ARXIVE, following the 5W framework (Why, Who, What, Where/How, When). It is structured as follows:

- **Section 1:** C&D Framework - outlines the overall approach, objectives, audiences, content, channels, and timeline.
- **Section 2:** Open Call Promotion - details the strategy for the two FSTP Open Calls.
- **Section 3:** Governance & Partner Responsibilities - defines roles and coordination processes.
- **Section 4:** Monitoring, KPIs & Evaluation - presents performance indicators and evaluation methodology.

1. Communication and Dissemination Framework

Communication and dissemination are integrated into the project from the outset and form part of each project phase. These activities are designed to address specific objectives and effectively engage relevant audiences. As the project progresses, they evolve to respond to stakeholders' needs and ensure that the project's outcomes are widely shared, applied, and sustained over time.

- **Communication:** Starts at the project's early stage and continues throughout to raise awareness, strengthen the project's identity, and actively engage stakeholders.
- **Dissemination:** Begins once results are ready to be shared with the public and continues as new findings are produced.

The ARXIVE C&D strategy complies with EU visibility requirements, GDPR, and ethical standards, while aligning with the ECCCH branding and dissemination framework. All communication materials will appropriately acknowledge EU funding.

Language: Most C&D activities will be delivered in English. However, specific materials (e.g. press releases, Open Call materials, and activities related to Stakeholder Hubs) may be published in other languages as appropriate.

1.1. Why - C&D Purpose and Objectives

The following six objectives guide all C&D activities throughout the project lifecycle:

- **C&D Objective 1 - Maximise Visibility:** Raise awareness across cultural heritage, research, innovation, and policy communities.
- **C&D Objective 2 - Ensure High-Quality Open Call Participation:** Promote FSTP funding transparently and attract strong applicants.
- **C&D Objective 3 - Disseminate Scientific Excellence:** Publish high-impact peer-reviewed research and technical outputs.
- **C&D Objective 4 - Support Policy Uptake:** Produce actionable policy recommendations and engage regulators.
- **C&D Objective 5 - Build Ecosystem & Synergies:** Strengthen collaboration within ECCCH and with sister projects.
- **C&D Objective 6 - Ensure Sustainability & Exploitation:** Promote long-term uptake beyond the project's duration.

1.2. Who: Target Audiences and Key Messages

ARXIVE undertook an initial stakeholder mapping exercise, identifying key stakeholders critical to the project's success. The stakeholder list will be regularly updated throughout the project to reflect any changes and ensure ongoing relevance. Stakeholders are classified into three tiers:

- **Primary Stakeholders:** Directly involved in core activities; have significant impact on ARXIVE's success and adoption of tools and methodologies.
- **Secondary Stakeholders:** Indirectly involved, supporting activities or benefiting from results; crucial for broader engagement and eventual project impact.
- **Tertiary Stakeholders:** The wider public, civil society, and media who play a role in raising awareness and disseminating project results.

Figure 1 - ARXIVE Stakeholder Map

Category	Target Group	Key Message	Engagement Goals	Channels (incl. social media)
Primary	TG1 - Cultural Heritage Professionals Archivists, conservators, museum & library managers	ARXIVE provides practical, AI-powered tools to improve documentation, preservation, and accessibility of cultural heritage assets.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adoption of ARXIVE tools in daily workflows Participation in workshops and pilot activities Contribution to co-creation processes 	FSTP projects, ICOM/ICCROM/NEMO networks, CH partners, MoUs, Vox Pop
	TG2 - Scientific Community Academia, universities, research infrastructures	ARXIVE advances interdisciplinary research at the intersection of AI, semantic technologies, and cultural heritage.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citation and reuse of ARXIVE datasets Collaboration in conferences, workshops, and joint publications Integration of ARXIVE tools into research infrastructures 	Peer-reviewed open-access publications, EUROMED/ISWC/IFLA/TPDL conferences, Zenodo, OpenAIRE
	TG3 - Tech Providers & SMEs Software developers, AI companies, startups, media artists	ARXIVE offers opportunities for innovation, collaboration, and funding through Open Calls and pilot activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High-quality applications to Open Calls 	Digital Innovation Hubs, S+T+ARTS network, Digital Heritage International Conference
	TG4 - Open Call Applicants	Funding opportunity, eligibility criteria, and innovation support via FSTP grants.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High-quality applications to Open Calls 	Project website, social media, webinars, EU portals, partner networks
Secondary	TG5 - Policymakers	ARXIVE contributes evidence-based insights and policy recommendations supporting Europe's digital heritage strategy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uptake of project findings into policy discussions Participation in Policy Labs 	Targeted briefings, European and international policy networks, Policy Labs, Advisory Board
	TG6 - ECCCH Governance	ARXIVE outputs are designed for long-term integration within ECCCH infrastructure beyond the project duration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to interoperability standards 	ECCCH collaborative editorial platform, ECCCH events, social media, press releases, policy briefs
	TG7 - Sister Projects	ARXIVE promotes cross-project learning, joint workshops, shared dissemination, and co-authored publications where relevant.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Joint workshops and dissemination events Cross-referencing results and shared visibility Co-authored publications or joint policy contributions 	Joint workshops and events, collaborative social media campaigns
Tertiary	TG8 - Civil Society & Media	ARXIVE enhances access to Europe's cultural heritage and demonstrates the societal value of EU-funded innovation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public engagement in exhibitions and events Increased trust in EU-funded research 	Universities, civil society actors, NGOs, media outlets, Vox Pop

Table 1 Target Groups, Key Messages, Goals, Channels

Additionally, WP1 will map and establish local, intersectional, and participatory stakeholder “hubs” in Germany, Greece, Portugal, Spain, and Cyprus to foster collaboration and ensure diverse perspectives inform ARXIVE. Two hubs per country will be developed collaboratively by research, practice, and industry-oriented partners within the consortium.

1.3. What: Content Types and Outputs

ARXIVE's outputs will span scientific, technical, and communication scopes, organised into the following categories:

1. **Technical Reports and Scientific Publications:** Detailed papers on activities, findings, and outcomes, aimed at researchers, academia, and technical experts.
2. **Toolkits:** Practical guides for community organisations, policymakers, and practitioners within CH.
3. **Policy Briefs:** Summaries of policy recommendations and guidance on integrating ARXIVE solutions within workflows.
4. **Communication Materials:** Factsheets, infographics, videos, and social media content for the general public and specific stakeholder groups.
5. **Webinars, Workshops, and Conferences:** Live and recorded events where key results are presented and stakeholders discuss project progress and insights.
6. **Capacity Building Materials:** Resources for training stakeholders, providing them with the tools and knowledge to implement ARXIVE solutions.

1.3.1. Content Promotion Guidelines

Content Type	Promotion Strategy
Technical Reports & Scientific Publications	Use charts and graphs; highlight key findings with callouts or pull quotes.
Toolkits	Include step-by-step instructions, diagrams, and case studies.
Policy Briefs	Use concise language, data visualisations, and infographics; highlight key takeaways.
Factsheets	High-quality visuals, short headlines, and colourful designs to attract attention.
Videos and Social Media Content	Showcase achievements with dynamic visuals and testimonials; use engaging captions and subtitles for accessibility.
Webinars, Workshops, and Conferences	Provide visually appealing slides and interactive polls; provide post-event summaries to participants.
Capacity Building Materials	Include diagrams, quizzes, and interactive activities.

1.3.2. Social Media Content Categories

Content Category	Primary Target Groups	C&D Objective
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<p>1. Open Call Promotion</p>	<p>Launch announcements Eligibility explanations Deadline reminders Webinar invitations FAQs & testimonials</p>	<p>TG3 Tech Providers & SMEs TG4 Open Call Applicants</p>	<p>C&D Objective 2</p>
<p>2. Pilot & Open Call Success Stories</p>	<p>Before/after use cases Short interviews with pilot partners "Behind the scenes" content</p>	<p>TG1 CH Professionals; TG3 Tech Providers & SMEs</p>	<p>C&D Objective 1 & 6</p>
<p>3. Scientific Dissemination</p>	<p>Publication announcements Conference presentations Dataset releases (Zenodo/OpenAIRE) Technical blog posts Research milestones</p>	<p>TG2 Scientific Community</p>	<p>C&D Objective 3</p>
<p>4. Event Participation</p>	<p>Conference participation announcements Live updates from workshops Photos from booths/presentations Post-event summaries</p>	<p>TG1; TG2; TG3</p>	<p>C&D Objective 1 & 5</p>
<p>5. Policy Highlights</p>	<p>Policy brief releases Key recommendations Insights from Policy Labs Alignment with EU strategies Contributions to ECCCH governance</p>	<p>TG5 Policymakers</p>	<p>C&D Objective 4</p>

6. ECCCH Collaboration	Collaboration with EU-funded projects Synergies with related initiatives Joint events and workshops	TG6 ECCCH governance; TG7 Sister Projects	C&D Objective 2&4
7. Consortium Expertise	Showcasing partner expertise Insights from consortium leaders Highlighting key contributions to milestones	TG7 Sister Projects	C&D Objective 1&3

1.4. Where and How: Communication Channels and Tools

This section outlines the tools and channels used to present project results and information. The project’s communication strategy focuses predominantly on digital channels, including the website, social media, and video content. Printed material is also foreseen to support external events. INOVA+ will regularly assess the project’s online presence and evaluate its impact.

1.4.1. Visual Identity

ARXIVE's visual identity enhances its image in both online and on-site communications, making it easily recognisable. All dissemination materials take into consideration this visual identity, which includes the logotype, typography, graphic elements, brand image, and templates.

- **Logo:** Designed to visually represent the core concept of “cultural heritage connected”.
- **Font:** JOST is used across the website and all public-facing communication. ARIAL is used in office templates, internal documents, and shared institutional files.
- **Slogan:** *Heritage, connected*
- **Tagline:** *A collaborative resource for cultural heritage*

The slogan and tagline may be adapted according to project activities and promotion needs (for example, when attending specific events or launching materials and publications).

Figure 2 ARXIVE Logo

1.4.2. Communication Materials

Communication materials are essential tools created to convey information, raise awareness, and engage target audiences. For ARXIVE, the following initial communication materials have been developed, such as: Word Template, PPT Template, Social media templates, and 1 ECCCH Roll-up.

Figure 3 ARXIVE templates

To support partners when referring to ARXIVE, an ARXIVE Language Toolkit has been compiled, providing adjectives and keywords related to the project across four dimensions: Heritage & Research, Digital & Technology, Values & Approach, and Impact & Benefits. The full toolkit is available in the ARXIVE Drive. (Annex 1)

1.4.3. Publications and Media

Press releases will be issued at key milestones to highlight significant achievements, such as pilot activities, publication of results, and participation in major events.

ARXIVE will prioritise high-quality scientific dissemination as a core pathway for maximising research impact. The consortium aims to publish at least 7 peer-reviewed scientific articles in high-impact journals such as the Journal of Cultural Heritage, Heritage, JOCCH, and the Semantic Web Journal. Partners will also present results at major international conferences including EUROMED, ICOM, IFLA, ISWC, TPD, and ECAI.

Table 2 ARXIVE Scientific Dissemination

Beneficiary	Conference / Journal	Target Group
NLG	ICOM Conference	Cultural Heritage (museums, preservation)
NLG	Metadata and Semantics Research Conference	Interdisciplinary
NLG	IFLA Congress	Libraries and information services
FORTH	EUROMED Conference	Cultural Heritage Sector
FORTH	Heritage Journal	Cultural Heritage Sector
FORTH	JOCCH Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage	Cultural Heritage Sector
FORTH	Journal of Cultural Heritage	Cultural Heritage Sector
FORTH	International Journal of Cultural Heritage	Cultural Heritage Sector
OKFGR	Journal of Web Semantics	Knowledge Management
OKFGR	Semantic Web Journal	Knowledge Management
OKFGR, LUH	International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC)	Knowledge Representation
LUH	International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries	Knowledge Management
LUH, FhG	Joint Conference on Digital Libraries	Digital Libraries
LUH	ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management	Digital Libraries
LUH	European Conference on Artificial Intelligence	Knowledge Management
LUH	International Conference on Knowledge Capture	Artificial Intelligence
LUH, FhG	International World Wide Web Conference	Semantic Web
FhG	Digital Humanities Conference	Digital Humanities Sector
FhG	Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology CAA Conference	Archaeology and Digital Humanities
FhG	CIPA Heritage Documentation bi-annual Symposium 2027 (Conference)	Cultural Heritage Sector

1.4.4. Website

ARXIVE's website (<https://arxive-eccch.eu/about/>) is the central platform for communication and dissemination. It is organised as follows:

- **Home:** Overview of the project's main goal and highlights.
- **About:** Introduces the project's mission, vision, and consortium partners.
- **Resources:** Access to project materials, reports, publications, and documentation.
- **News and Events:** Updates on project progress, upcoming events, and milestones.
- **Contact Us:** A contact form to facilitate communication with the project team.

The website will be developed in three phases. Phase 1 (launched February 2026) includes core information about the project. Phase 2 (September 2026) will introduce sections dedicated to the FSTP scheme and Vox Pop activities. Phase 3 will progressively incorporate project results including FSTP impacts, public deliverables, policy briefs, and a repository of scientific publications. Monthly analytics will track page views, traffic sources, and visitor profiles.

Figure 4 ARXIVE website

Data Protection

ARXIVE is committed to complying with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Key data subject rights respected include: Right to Access, Right to Rectification, Right to Erasure, Right to Restriction of Processing, Right to Data Portability, and Right to Object. All personal data processed via the contact form, media consent, and cookie usage will be handled in full compliance with GDPR, with clear and accessible policies published on the project website.

1.4.5. ECCCH Alignment

Given the typology of this project, ARXIVE will closely follow and disseminate the ECHOES-ECCCH.EU communication guidelines, including adherence to the URL structure, website layout,

social media strategy (post structure, hashtags, and visual assets), and contributing to the collaborative editorial platform populated by all ECCCH partners.

1.4.6. Social Media

ARXIVE's social media channels will promote awareness and reach relevant target audiences. The project will primarily use LinkedIn (targeting institutions, policymakers, and researchers), YouTube (tutorials, interviews, and event recordings), and Instagram (engaging visuals and short reels). ARXIVE has been active on LinkedIn since January 2026.

Figure 5 ARXIVE LinkedIn

Table 3 ARXIVE platform content focus

Platform	Content Focus	Frequency	Link
LinkedIn	Participation in international, national, and regional events Updates on project milestones, deliverables, and publications Project events (workshops, webinars) Policy insights and stakeholder testimonials Cross-promotion with EU and sister projects	Twice a week and whenever relevant	https://www.linkedin.com/company/arxive-eccch/
YouTube	Tutorials and guides for capacity building Recordings of webinars, workshops, and public events	When relevant	https://www.youtube.com/@ARXIVE_ECCCH
Instagram	Outcomes from Open Calls GLAM-focused content	When relevant (after Open Call launch)	@arxive_eccch
Zenodo	Dissemination	When results are available	@ARXIVE_ECCCH
OpenAire	Dissemination	When results are available	ARXIVE ECCCH

Key hashtags: #DigitalHeritage #AI #OpenScience #HorizonEU #EUresearch #Innovation #DigitalTransformation. **Key accounts:** sister projects + @ECHOES EU, @European Research Executive Agency (REA)

A weekly posting schedule will be maintained and accessible on the ARXIVE Drive.

Primary phase	Monthly theme	Timeline focus
Preparation	Project launch, identity and mission	Kick-off communication kit, branding, website foundation, ecosystem building starts
Preparation	Consortium expertise and ecosystem	Website visibility, partner introductions, baseline assessment begins
Preparation	Stakeholder hubs kickoff	Stakeholder hub mapping and establishment begins (M3-M12)
Preparation	Challenges in digital heritage workflows	Stakeholder engagement and user-need discovery continue
Preparation	Baseline assessment and pilot-specific needs	Pilot-specific needs and Open Call framework preparation intensify (from M5)
Preparation	Tool concepts and semantic interoperability	Pilot implementation preparation and technology framing continue (pilot implementation M6-M26)
Preparation	Data pipelines, 3D and annotation workflows	Methods, workflows and tool-building narratives mature
Preparation	Community warm-up before Open Calls	Community warm-up, outreach and Open Call pre-launch visibility
Preparation + Open Call Launch & Awareness	Open Call runway	Open Call preparation: landing pages, materials, dissemination platforms
Preparation + Open Call Launch & Awareness	Open Call launch	Open Call launch: website publication, press release, social announcements, outreach
Open Call Launch & Awareness	Eligibility, themes and application support	Applicant support, theme explanation, partner amplification and webinars
Open Call Launch & Awareness	Webinars, FAQs and deadline reminders	FAQs, reminders, deadline support; training materials development starts (M12)

Figure 6 ARXIVE Communication Monthly Overview

1.4.7. Advisory Board

ARXIVE has established a high-level Advisory Board of 3 members to provide strategic guidance throughout the project, representing the fields of cultural heritage preservation, historical bibliography, and media heritage. The Board meets bi-annually. The most relevant project communications and invitations will be shared with the Advisory Board to support dissemination through their networks.

1.5. When: Timeline and Project Phases

C&D activities will be implemented throughout the 36-month project duration, structured into four phases:

Table 4 ARXIVE communication phases

	Phase 1: Preparation (M1-10)	Phase 2: Open Call Launch & Awareness (M9-14)	Phase 3: Active Promotion & Engagement (M15-24)	Phase 4: Expansion, Policy Uptake & Sustainability (M25-36)
Key Activities	Finalise Communication Kit (branding, templates) Launch project website with essential project information	Develop and publish Open Call materials (launch kits, landing pages, FAQs) Distribute press releases; inform	Social media campaigns highlighting successful applicants, testimonials, and Open Call impact Publish research results in peer-	Promote long-term uptake of ARXIVE solutions beyond project duration Ensure all deliverables and datasets are publicly available on open-access platforms

Preliminary stakeholder mapping	newsletters and posting boards	reviewed journals; share on Zenodo	Hold Policy Labs to discuss final recommendations for European cultural heritage policies
Develop social media strategy and content calendar	Promote Open Calls on LinkedIn, partner networks, EU channels	Present at international conferences and workshops	Publish final policy briefs and engage policymakers at European and national levels
	Organise Open Call Webinars	Showcase ARXIVE tools at industry events and digital heritage conferences	Organise final ARXIVE dissemination event
	Kick-start Vox Pop initiative	Engage policymakers in discussions about ARXIVE contributions	

Key tasks that serve as focal points for intensified communication efforts are:

- *Project kick-off (M1)*
- **T5.1** Baseline Assessment and Identification of Pilot-Specific Needs **(M1-M8)**
- **T7.2** Ecosystem building and collaboration with ECCCH projects **(M1-M36)**
- **T1.1** Mapping and establishment of participatory stakeholder **hubs (M3-M12)**
- **T5.3** Open Call Framework, publication and selection **(M5-M20)**
- **T5.2** Pilot Implementation **(M6-M26)**
- **T6.3** Virtual drop-in office hours for reborn articles production **(M12-M36)**
- **T5.4** Training materials development **(M12-M26)**
- **T7.4** Success stories, lessons learned, and policy recommendations **(M24-M36)**
- *Final Conference (M36)*

Figure 7 ARXIVE communication intensive activities

2. Open Call Promotion Strategy

ARXIVE will launch 2 concurrent Open Calls from November 2026 to February 2027, each supporting up to 10 third parties with €20,000 lump-sum grants:

- **Open Call #1 | Bibliography Beyond Boundaries:** Enhances the creation, enrichment, and refinement of annotated bibliographies linked to CHOs. Develops innovative

approaches for automating bibliographic annotation workflows and promoting collaborative work through the ECCCH platform.

- **Open Call #2 | Building Digital Narratives:** Emphasises the creation and deployment of digital storytelling techniques for documenting and interpreting CH fieldwork, in archaeological excavations and related research. Targets integration of innovative tools to improve data visualisation, analysis, and communication.

2.1. Promotion Materials and Channels

To ensure high-quality applications, ARXIVE Open Call promotion will include:

- Homepage and dedicated Open Call section on the website (including application documents and templates, guidelines for applicants, FAQs)
- 1 FAQ Webinar per Open Call
- Dedicated social media campaigns (LinkedIn, project website)
- Open Call partner materials including social media template posts with captions, outreach email, and press release in English (with request for partners to adapt to native languages if relevant)

The Open Calls will be promoted through: ARXIVE website, EU Funding & Tenders Portal, ECCCH Newsletter, AI-on-Demand, and S+T+ARTS.

2.2. Tentative Open Call Workflow

Table 5 Open Call Communication Workflow

Phase	Activities
Phase 1 - Preparation (T-2 Months before Call Launch)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finalise Application Kit • Create landing page • Identify dissemination platforms • Develop social media calendar
Phase 2 - Launch (Week 1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website publication • Press release • Social media announcement • Newsletter and posting boards distribution • Email outreach to networks
Phase 3 - Active Promotion (Weeks 2-8)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinar • Paid social campaign (if required) • Partner amplification
Phase 4 - Reminder Campaign (Final 2 Weeks)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Countdown posts
Phase 5 - Closure & Follow-Up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote selected projects

3. Governance and Partner Responsibilities

As WP7 (Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation, Sustainability) leader, INOVA+ is the main responsible party for the implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Plan, coordinating with the remaining partners across all work packages. INOVA+'s responsibilities include managing content creation, coordinating events, and tracking stakeholder engagement.

Partners will be regularly informed and actively involved in the project's C&D actions. Information and requests will be communicated via email and shared through the ARXIVE Drive. As WP7 leader, INOVA+ will discuss C&D needs during consortium meetings and establish a mini task-force when stronger communication efforts may be needed (e.g. Open Call dissemination).

INOVA+ has also created a tracking C&D Excel document available in the ARXIVE Drive where all partners should regularly update their participation in events or activities, list of publications, and share ideas for social media and website content.

Future events						
Add here conferences, events, publications or any D&C opportunity that you foresee						
Future event	Type	Organiser	Date	Location	Possible participant	URL

Figure 8 ARXIVE C&D Tracking Tool

3.1. Partner Roles

Table 6 Partner Roles

Partner	Responsibilities
INOVA+	<p>Communication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide updates during Consortium meetings, and establish dedicated task forces when needed (e.g Open Calls) • Coordinate the development and maintenance of the project website, ensuring regular updates. • Develop communication materials (factsheets, templates, infographics, Open Call promotional materials) and share with partners. • Implement the social media strategy and content calendar, and support partners' online engagement. <p>Dissemination:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinate the organisation of project events and ensure alignment of dissemination activities across all partners. • Support partners in delivering outreach and training activities, including the preparation of dissemination materials. <p>C&D Management:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review and validate C&D content produced by partners. Update the C&D plan when necessary to ensure KPIs are achieved. Prepare and distribute general press releases in accordance with LUH. Produce videos and other visual materials to support dissemination activities.
LUH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide support in defining suitable content for dissemination materials and review materials produced by partners. Lead the consortium's dissemination efforts and coordinate the dissemination of scientific, technical, and non-technical content, including participation in relevant events and joint scientific and technical publications.
Pilots (MMP, NLG)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote public awareness and identify, contact, and engage local and regional organisations to support outreach and collaboration.
Academic & Research Partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribute to scientific publications and disseminate research findings at relevant conferences and journals. Share results and updates through academic networks, publications, and other professional channels.
Technical Partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribute technical content for dissemination materials, such as manuals, case studies, and best practices. Share insights and expertise through workshops, webinars, and industry-focused events.
ALL PARTNERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribute to the strategy definition by listing communication channels and reporting all activities. Support all ARXIVE C&D activities as needed. Provide inputs and feedback on technical content for marketing materials. Support the organisation of and participation in events.

3.2. C&D General Guidelines for Partners

- **Project Visual Identity:** All partners must consistently use the project's official visual identity, including the project logo, EU funding logo, ECHOES logo, templates, and branding materials. The necessary files and guidelines are available in the ARXIVE Drive (**Annex 2**).
- **Project URL and Acknowledgement of EU Funding:** Partners must include the official project URL (<https://arxive-eccch.eu/>) and acknowledge EU funding in all relevant publications, communications, and public appearances.
 - *Recommended EU funding acknowledgement wording:* "This project is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement no.101233418 and is part of the ECCCH initiative. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not

necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.."

- **ECHOES:** ARXIVE is part of the ECCCH Cultural Heritage Cloud initiative, managed by the ECHOES PROJECT (<https://www.echoes-eccch.eu/>).
- **Coordination with INOVA+:** All partners must ensure that their activities align with INOVA+'s strategic direction and share any relevant updates with INOVA+ for validation before distribution.
- **Website Updates:** Partners should regularly post updates about project activities on their institutional websites. Brief updates should be uploaded to the shared dissemination folder in the ARXIVE Drive and a copy sent to INOVA+ for approval before public distribution.
- **Social Media Posts:** Partners should share project-related news on their social media accounts, tagging ARXIVE's official accounts, and are encouraged to share ARXIVE's social media posts to broaden outreach.
- **Event Participation:** Partners are expected to attend and actively participate in relevant events. After the event, partners should complete the events report template (see Annex) and send additional content (photos, videos, key information) to INOVA+.
- **Contributing to Dissemination Materials:** Partners are responsible for contributing content to dissemination materials. Content should be tailored to the specific needs of the targeted audience and uploaded to the shared folder for review and final approval by INOVA+.

4. Monitoring, KPIs and Evaluation

The following C&D KPIs (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation) have been defined to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of ARXIVE's C&D activities, knowledge transfer, and exploitation efforts.

4.1. KPI Targets by Channel

Table 7 KPI targets by channel

Channel / Activity	KPI Target (by M36)
Website	30,500 sessions total by M36; 3,500 unique users/month by M36
LinkedIn	+1,000 followers; +10k impressions
Instagram	+500 followers; 100 posts
Video & YouTube	+200 subscribers; +10 promo videos
Press Releases	+4 press releases/year (12 in total); +2 interviews/year (6 in total)
Conferences / Events	+12 events; +10 partnerships
Webinars & Workshops	+6 sessions hosted; +200 participants; 80% average satisfaction rate
Print Materials	+2,000 printed items distributed
Scientific Publications	+15 publications; +7 scientific conference presentations

EC Platforms	+6 news items
Policy Briefs & Papers	+5 policy briefs; +5 policymaker meetings
ECCCH Ecosystem Meetings	+50 MoUs
Training Materials	+300 CH professionals reached; +50 follow-ups from interested partners
Policy Labs	+2 Policy Labs; +4 Briefings

4.2. Monitoring and Evaluation Approach

- **Centralised Data Tracking:** KPIs will be monitored using a centralised Excel database hosted in the shared project folder, ensuring all relevant data is captured consistently and accurately.
- **Regular Updates:** Impact assessment will be conducted quarterly, with results shared within the consortium and communicated to stakeholders during regular WP7 project meetings and technical progress reports.
- **Stakeholder Feedback:** Post-event surveys, interviews, and focus groups will capture the satisfaction of stakeholders and gather suggestions for improving future activities.
- **Reporting and Adjustments:** Impact assessment results will be integrated into periodic project reports, with adjustments to project strategies made as necessary to improve impact and engagement.

4.3. Expected Results Assessment

Project impact will be assessed through the following quantitative and qualitative measures:

- **Website Traffic:** Monitoring the volume of visitors to the project website and the level of engagement to gauge public interest and awareness.
- **Press and Media Engagement:** Tracking the effectiveness of press releases, media coverage, and interviews to assess the project’s visibility in the public sphere.
- **Community Involvement:** Evaluating stakeholder engagement through event participation, feedback, and the dissemination of knowledge products such as publications and best-practice handbooks.
- **Social Media Impact:** Measuring social media engagement, including the growth of followers, interactions with posts, and the overall reach of the project’s social media platforms.

Conclusion

This deliverable establishes the initial framework for ARXIVE’s communication and dissemination activities throughout the project duration. By combining clear objectives, audience-specific

messages, partner responsibilities, Open Call promotion actions, and measurable KPIs, D7.1 provides a structured basis for ensuring that project results are communicated consistently, disseminated effectively, and aligned with ECCCH and EU visibility requirements. Its implementation will be monitored on a quarterly basis and adjusted when needed in response to project progress, stakeholder feedback, and emerging opportunities for impact. Communication and dissemination efforts, as well as D7.1, will be continuously updated according to the project's needs. Periodic updates will be provided in D7.2 Communication and Dissemination Report I (M16) and D7.3 Communication and Dissemination Report II (M28).

ANNEX 1

ARXIVE language toolkit

31 03 2026

Inês Francisco

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ARXIVE Language Toolkit

This toolkit brings together a set of adjectives and keywords that reflect the core dimensions of the project: what ARXIVE works on, how it operates, the values that guide it, and the impact it aims to create. The goal is to support partners when referring to ARXIVE in a consistent way across documents and presentations. Together, these terms capture the project's commitment to advancing cultural heritage research through digital innovation, open collaboration, and sustainable knowledge infrastructures at the European level.

Table 1 ARXIVE Language Toolkit (v1)

Heritage & Research (<i>What ARXIVE works on</i>)	Digital & Technology (How ARXIVE operates)	Values & Approach (ARXIVE as a project)	Impact & Benefits (<i>Why ARXIVE matters</i>)
Cultural (<i>relating to shared European heritage</i>)	Digital-first (designed primarily for digital environments)	Collaborative (built through partnerships and shared effort)	Accessible (<i>easy to reach and understand for diverse users</i>)
Archaeological (<i>fieldwork, excavation, material evidence</i>)	Cloud-based (integrated within the Cultural Heritage Cloud)	Connected (linking people, data and institutions)	Inclusive (<i>addressing different audiences and stakeholders</i>)
Archival (<i>records, collections, long-term memory</i>)	Interoperable (systems and data that work together)	Open (supporting open science and access)	Shared (<i>knowledge distributed across the community</i>)
Documentary (<i>structured documentation and metadata</i>)	Data-driven (structured, searchable, reusable information)	Transparent (clear processes and traceable data)	Structured (<i>information organised and usable</i>)
Scholarly (<i>academic research and scientific rigour</i>)	Modular (built from components that can evolve)	Trusted (reliable, credible and institutionally sound)	Robust (<i>technically and conceptually solid</i>)
Contextual (<i>heritage understood within its historical and social frame</i>)	Scalable (able to grow across projects and institutions)	Sustainable (designed for long-term use and impact)	Continuity-driven (<i>ensuring long-term preservation of knowledge</i>)
Evidence-based (<i>grounded in verified data and research</i>)	Intelligent (supporting analysis and informed decision-making)	Human-centred (technology serving people and research needs)	Knowledge-oriented (<i>focused on understanding, not just storage</i>)
	Future-ready (prepared for long-term technological evolution)	European (aligned with EU values and cross-border collaboration)	Research-enabling (<i>supporting innovation and discovery</i>)

Last updated: March 2026

ANNEX 2: ARXIVE Visual Guide

COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES

ARXIVE

SYMBOL

LOGOTYPE

PRIMARY LOGO USAGE

ARXIVE is part of the ECCCH ecosystem and must be consistently co-branded with ECHOES to ensure alignment, visibility and coherence across all communication materials.

ARXIVE

VERTICAL LOGO USAGE

ARXIVE

LIGHT APRICOT

Openness

Accessibility, warmth and human presence

#ffcb97

R0 G0 B0

C0% M0% Y0% K0%

BURNT ORANGE

Discovery

Exploration, action and archaeological excavation

#ff7348

R0 G0 B0

C0% M0% Y0% K0%

DARK AUBERGINE

Continuity

Memory, depth and long-term knowledge preservation

#451768

R0 G0 B0

C0% M0% Y0% K0%

ELECTRIC VIOLET

Connectivity

Intelligence, innovation and digital networks

#7126db

R0 G0 B0

C0% M0% Y0% K0%

PALE LILAC

Accessibility

Open knowledge and inclusive digital platforms

#ffc5f3

R0 G0 B0

C0% M0% Y0% K0%

TYPOGRAPHY SYSTEM

EXPRESSIVE TYPOGRAPHY (BRAND & PUBLISHING)

Where ARXIVE's identity, hierarchy and visual voice take shape.

Used across the website, publications, presentations and all public-facing communication.

HEADLINES: CHILLAX (CAPS)

Body text: Jost

FUNCTIONAL TYPOGRAPHY (OPERATIONAL USE)

Ensuring clarity, accessibility and seamless collaboration.

Used in office templates, internal documents and shared institutional files.

ARIAL

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PRESERVING
HERITAGE.
STRUCTURING
KNOWLEDGE.
CONNECTING
RESEARCH.

ARXIVE
ARXIVE
ARXIVE
ARXIVE

ARXIVE is a collaborative digital platform dedicated to the documentation, preservation and sharing of cultural heritage and archaeological knowledge.

It connects fieldwork, archives and research through structured digital tools and cloud-based infrastructure.

By bridging heritage and technology, ARXIVE supports innovation, accessibility and long-term knowledge continuity across Europe.

ARXIVE

Consortium

